

The Effect Of Communication And Teamwork On Employee Performance At The Regional Secretariat Sibolga City

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Abstrak: *This study aims to determine the effect of Communication (X1) and Teamwork (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) at the Regional Secretariat of Sibolga City. This research employs a quantitative method with a descriptive approach, utilizing a sample of 46 respondents. Data analysis was performed using Multiple Linear Regression. The results indicate a strong correlation, with coefficients of 0.674 for Communication and 0.628 for Teamwork. The Coefficient of Determination (R²) is 0.560, implying that 56% of the variance in Employee Performance is simultaneously influenced by Communication and Teamwork, while the remaining 44% is attributed to external factors. Partial testing (t-test) and simultaneous testing (F-test) confirm that both variables have a positive and significant impact on performance.*

Keywords: *Teamwork, Employee Performance, Communication*

INTRODUCTION

The most important resource of an organization is its people, those who contribute their energy, talent, creativity, and efforts to the organization. Therefore, employees are the key to the success of a company. For this reason, every employee is required to have knowledge, skills, and abilities, as well as experience, motivation, self-discipline, and a high work ethic, so that employees will also improve, leading to the achievement of organizational goals. The success of an organization is measured by its success in achieving its goals.

An employee's performance is a very important starting point for creating work effectiveness. An organization will not function properly without human resources. Employees have control as planners, implementers, and controllers who always play an active role in realizing the organization's goals. They are the actors who support the achievement of goals with their thoughts, feelings, and desires that can influence attitudes towards the work given, whether positive or negative.

Effectiveness is a key element of organizational activities in achieving predetermined goals or objectives. When viewed from the perspective of success in achieving goals, effectiveness focuses on the level of achievement of organizational goals. Furthermore, in terms of timeliness, effectiveness is the achievement of various predetermined targets on

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time using specific resources that have been allocated to carry out various activities. Next, the results or quality achieved can be compared with the predetermined quality. If the work performed by employees is better than what has been determined, then these employees are classified as effective employees. It should be understood that every leader is responsible for guiding their employees in the right direction so that the organization's goals can be achieved accurately.

Communication is one of the tools for improving employee work effectiveness, for monitoring or observing the implementation of company management that attempts to direct the organization's goals within the company so that the performance carried out by company management can run more efficiently and smoothly. What is monitored or regulated in the management control system is the performance of managers in managing the company, for which they will be accountable to stakeholders. Effective communication must be established within the organization to achieve organizational goals.

The purpose of communication within an organization is to create mutual understanding so that there is equality in the frame of reference and commonality among members of the organization. Poor communication skills will result in poor interactions, so that internal conflicts often arise within organizations, factions begin to form, arguments occur due to personal issues, and everyone insists on their own opinions. Communication is minimal because people are no longer willing to listen to each other. The communication process can also sometimes influence a person's perspective in understanding the message being conveyed.

Communication within an organization must be viewed from various perspectives, namely: first, communication between superiors and subordinates; second, between one employee and another; and third, between employees and superiors. Among these three aspects of communication, communication between subordinates and leaders is one of the problems that exists in the Regional Secretariat, which was obtained from initial observations by directly observing the interaction processes between employees and leaders. Relationships can be maintained through communication between leaders and employees and among employees themselves, with the aim of maintaining cooperation so that organizational performance is truly maximized, because effective communication is considered the main key to success in relation to efforts for change.

Teamwork is a critical factor influencing employee performance. Effective and coordinated collaboration leads to superior achievements and is often considered the optimal organizational solution. Previous research by Hermanto (2020) emphasizes that teamwork significantly impacts employee output. In practice, however, communication gaps often hinder performance. For instance, at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, initial observations revealed a lack of solid teamwork and openness in sharing ideas, which resulted in performance levels that fell below leadership expectations.

Teamwork is an important aspect that supports work effectiveness in an organization. Team members must be able to work together and have confidence in the abilities of their colleagues. Therefore, the quality of employee work is determined by the extent to which the organization is able to manage human resources to have a commitment to mutually support the achievement of organizational and personal goals. This commitment

can be realized by reflecting on *teamwork*, which is group cooperation for a common goal. This statement is in line with what Lawasi (2017:51) said, that teamwork is the most effective way to unite all employees in carrying out their tasks to achieve the company's goals with good results.

The Regional Secretariat is a government agency in Sibolga City that assists regional heads (regents/mayors/governors) in policy formulation, coordination of regional apparatus tasks, monitoring and evaluation of policy implementation, and administrative services. Therefore, the importance of the secretariat's duties, functions, and authorities for regional development is closest to that of the regional head. The regional secretariat must work hard to ensure that the regional head's programs are implemented properly. To achieve these programs, Regional Secretariat employees must carry out their duties or work effectively. Unfortunately, in practice, it is often found that employees do not work as effectively as they should. For example, employees often arrive late for work, even leaving the office before the end of working hours. In addition, the facilities available to support employees in completing their work are still minimal, so that sometimes the work is unsatisfactory. This is a demand for the regional secretariat government to be more effective in carrying out its duties and responsibilities in order to achieve the minimum service standards and excellent service designed by the government to remain effective.

From the above explanation and the author's initial observations at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, it is known that there is still a lack of communication between employees in the performance of their duties, so that the work done is not as desired. For example, when requesting items such as computers from the organization department to the general department, employee performance is not optimal due to the lack of solid teamwork among employees in carrying out their work. This is because there are still employees who do not understand the meaning of good teamwork. There are still employees who are not open in providing good ideas and suggestions for completing work within the agency. As a result, performance does not meet the expectations of the leadership. In relation to the background of the above problem, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title "The Effect of Communication and Teamwork on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat."

RESEARCH METHOD

The type of research used in this study is a quantitative research method with a descriptive approach. Quantitative research is defined as "a research method based on positivism philosophy, used to study a specific population or sample, collecting data using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing" (Sugiyono, 2017:17).

The type of data used in this study is quantitative data. According to Kuncoro (2016:145), "Quantitative data is data measured on a numerical scale (numbers), which can be divided into interval data and ratio data." According to Arikunto (2016:129), the source of data in research is "the subject from which data can be obtained." In this study, the author used two sources of data, namely primary and secondary.

The data collection techniques used by the author in this study are as follows:

- a. Literature Study, which involves studying various reading sources closely related to the research problem, both in the form of scientific books and laws and regulations.
- b. Field Study, which involves collecting data directly from the research location by:
 1. Observation. This involves conducting direct research on the object being discussed in order to obtain data.
 2. Interviews. A method of data collection by conducting face-to-face interviews with parties who can provide information about communication, teamwork, and employee performance, which are the factors of the research.
 3. Questionnaires. This is a data collection technique by submitting written questions to respondents () which must be answered in writing by the respondents.

The data analysis technique in this study is adapted to quantitative research methods, emphasizing hypothesis testing through statistical analysis. The data analysis techniques used in this study are: research instrument testing, classical assumption testing, determination testing, simple linear regression testing, and hypothesis testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Research Instrument Test

Validation Test of Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance Variables

The results of the validity test of the variables of Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of the Validity Test of Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance

No Item	$r_{\text{calculate}}$	r_{critical}	Conclusio
Variable X1 (Communication)			
Item 1	0.657	0.3	Valid
Item 2	0.606	0.30	Valid
Item 3	0.732	0.30	Valid
Item 4	0.457	0.30	Valid
Item 5	0.445	0.30	Valid
Item 6	0.640	0.30	Valid
Item 7	0.505	0.30	Valid
Item 8	0.459	0.30	Valid
Item 9	0.560	0.30	Valid
Item 10	0.657	0.30	Valid
Variable X2 (Teamwork)			
Item 1	0.713	0	Valid
Item 2	0.539	0.30	Valid
Item 3	0.485	0.30	Valid
Item 4	0.674	0.30	Valid
Item 5	0.618	0.30	Valid
Item 6	0.723	0.30	Valid
Item 7	0.441	0.30	Valid
Item 8	0.679	0.30	Valid
Item 9	0.571	0.30	Valid
Item 10	0.713	0.30	Valid
Variable Y (Employee Performance)			

Item 1	0.731	0.30	Valid
Item 2	0.750	0.30	Valid
Item 3	0.691	0.30	Valid
Item 4	0.638	0.30	Valid
Item 5	0.619	0.30	Valid
Item 6	0.731	0.30	Valid
Item 7	0.568	0.30	Valid
Item 8	0.622	0.30	Valid
Item 9	0.689	0.30	Valid
Item 10	0.731	0.30	Valid

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that all questionnaire items for the research variables, namely Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance, show figures greater than 0.30. Thus, all items for the Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance variables above are declared valid and meet the requirements as measurement tools in this study.

Reliability Test of Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance

The results of the reliability test for the Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance variable questionnaires can be seen in Table 2.

**Table 2. Reliability Test Results
Communication Variables, Teamwork, and Employee Performance**

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
1	Communication	0.862	Reliable
2	Teamwork	0.885	Reliable
3	Employee	0.911	Reliable

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

Based on the results of the reliability test of the research instrument in Table 2, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* value of each item in each variable of Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance is > 0.60 and is declared reliable.

Normality Test

There are two ways to detect whether the residuals are normally distributed or not, namely through graphical analysis and statistical testing. In this study, both methods were used:

Graphical analysis

The results of the normality test can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Histogram Graph of Communication, Teamwork, and Employee Performance Variables

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

Figure 1 shows that the variables are normally distributed. This is indicated by the distribution of data that does not deviate to the left or right. The results of the *P-Plot* analysis of the normality test can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

In Figure 2, the *P-P plot* shows that the points are scattered around the diagonal line and follow the diagonal line, so it can be concluded that the data obtained is normally distributed.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Source: *Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)*

Based on the figure above, the points are scattered randomly and spread both above and below zero on the Y-axis, so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

Coefficient of Determination

**Table 3. Coefficient of Determination Output
Model Summary^b**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.761	.580	.560	4.37026	2.322

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teamwork, Communication

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: *Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)*

From the above calculation, a coefficient of determination of 0.560 can be obtained. This means that 56% of the variation in Employee Performance (Variable Y) is determined by the independent variables of Communication (Variable X1) and Teamwork (Variable X2) simultaneously, and the remaining 44% is determined by other factors not discussed in this study.

Multiple Linear Regression

To determine the significant effect between variables X and Y, a simple linear regression calculation was performed as follows:

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Coefficient Output Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
1.(Constant)	5.247	4.672		1,123	.268		
Communication	.509	.117	.487	4,348	.000	.780	1,282
Teamwork	.399	.112	.400	3,571	.001	.780	1,282

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

From the table above, the regression equation $Y = 0.5247 + 0.509 X_1 + 0.399 X_2$, can be interpreted as follows:

- Constant (5.247): This value indicates that if Communication and Teamwork are constant (zero), the baseline Employee Performance score is 5.247.
- Communication (X₁) Coefficient (0.509): This positive coefficient indicates that every unit increase in Communication will lead to a 0.509 increase in Employee Performance, assuming other variables remain constant.
- Teamwork (X₂) Coefficient (0.399): Similarly, every unit increase in Teamwork results in a 0.399 improvement in Employee Performance.

Hypothesis Testing

T-test (Partial Test)

The T-test (partial test) was conducted to determine the individual or partial effect of communication and teamwork on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, the results of which can be seen in Table 4. Based on Table 4 above, the individual or partial effects of Communication and Teamwork on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat can be explained as follows:

- Communication (X₁): The calculated t-value of 4.348 exceeds the t-table value of 2.01410 (4.348 > 2.01410) with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, H₁ is accepted, proving that Communication has a significant partial effect on Employee Performance.
- Teamwork (X₂): The calculated t-value of 3.571 is greater than the t-table value of 2.01410 (3.571 > 2.01410) with a significance of 0.001 < 0.05. Therefore, H₂ is accepted, confirming that Teamwork significantly influences Employee Performance.

F Test (Anova Test)

The F test (Anova test) was conducted to determine or explain whether Communication and Teamwork have a combined or simultaneous effect on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, the results of which can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. F Test (Anova Test) Results
ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1131,954	2	565,977	29,634	.000 ^b
Residual	821,263	43	19,099		
Total	1,953,217	45			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teamwork, Communication

Source: Research Results, 2025 (SPSS26)

Based on Table 5 above, the combined or simultaneous effect of communication and teamwork on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat can be explained as follows:

- From the results of conventional testing at a significance level = 0.05 with $df_1 = 2$ and $df_2 = 43$ (obtained from the results of $df, (n-k-1) = (46-2-1) = 43$, it is known that $F_{table} = 3.21$ and $F_{count} = 29.634$. Because $F_{calculated} > F_{table}$, H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted, thus Team Communication and Cooperation affects Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat.

From the results of testing using SPSS, namely by looking at the significance probability (P-value) = 0.000 or 0% less than 5%, it can be said that the variables of Communication and Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Communication on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat

According to Mangkunegara (2017:145), "Communication is the process of transferring information, ideas, and understanding from one person to another with the hope that the other person can interpret it in accordance with the intended purpose."

Based on the results of the study, it shows that communication has a significant effect on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat. The T-test conducted showed that the calculated t-value $>$ t-table ($4.348 > 2.01410$) with a significance level of 0.000 or less than 5%. therefore H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the proposed hypothesis that communication has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat is proven and accepted as true. The form of communication that takes place at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat is already

quite good. Communication at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat will more or less improve employee performance.

This is in line with previous research on the effect of communication on employee performance, namely Cahyani (2024). In her study entitled *The Effect of Communication and Teamwork on the Performance of PT Zr Employees*, the aim was to determine the effect of communication and teamwork on the performance of PT Zr employees. This was a quantitative study. The sampling technique used was saturated sampling, where the population and sample size were 50 respondents. Data collection was carried out using questionnaires that had been tested for validity and reliability. Data processing was carried out using *Statistical Program for Social Science (SPSS)* version 27. Data analysis was carried out using multiple linear regression analysis. The results of this study show that: (1) Communication has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (the t-value obtained is $4.502 > 2.011$ (t-table) with sig. $0.000 < 0.05$, meaning (α) or the significance value is less than 0.05). (2) Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (calculated t-value of $3.705 > 2.011$ (t-table) with sig. $0.001 < 0.05$ meaning (α) or a significance value smaller than 0.05). (3) Communication and Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on employee performance (calculated F value of $27.972 > 3.20$ (F table) with a sig. value of $0.000 < 0.05$ (α) or a significance value less than 0.05.

The Effect of Teamwork on the Performance of Sibolga City Regional Secretariat Employees

Teamwork is an activity carried out in groups to achieve a specific goal. Meanwhile, according to Busro (2018:305), "Teamwork is a group process in which members support and rely on each other to achieve a consensus."

Based on the results of the study, it shows that teamwork has a significant effect on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat. The T-test conducted showed that the calculated t-value $>$ t-table ($3.571 > 2.01410$) with a significance level of 0.001 or less than 5%. therefore H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the proposed hypothesis that teamwork has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat is proven and accepted as true.

The results of the study at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat are in line with the results of a previous study by Asykur (2024). *The Effect of Teamwork and Communication on Employee Performance at PT. ASDP Indonesia Ferry (Persero) Bangka Branch*. The purpose of the study was to determine whether employee performance at PT. ASDP Indonesia Ferry (Persero) Bangka Branch was influenced by teamwork and communication. The research sample consisted of 138 workers. For this survey, a sample of 58 respondents was selected randomly. The data collection method was using a questionnaire. The hypothesis test results show that the variables of teamwork and communication have a simultaneous, positive, and significant effect on employee performance at a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. Employee performance is influenced by the type of cooperation, and at a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be determined that the impact is positive and significant. Based on the partial effect of $0.014 < 0.05$ between the communication variable and employee performance, it can be stated that there is a positive and significant effect

between the communication factor and employee performance at PT. ASDP Indonesia Ferry (Persero) Bangka Branch.

The Influence of Communication and Teamwork on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat

Performance is a work process that produces work achieved by an employee in accordance with the work assigned to him/her within a certain period of time. Meanwhile, according to Hasibuan (2017:94), "Employee performance is the result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him/her based on competence, experience, sincerity, and time."

Based on the results of the analysis in this study, which shows that the variables of Communication (Variable X1) and Teamwork (Variable X2) have an effect on Employee Performance (Variable Y). These results can be seen from the F table value = 3.21 and F count = 29.634. Because the calculated $F >$ table F with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the proposed hypothesis that Communication and Teamwork have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat is proven and accepted as true.

The results of the research at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat are in line with the results of previous research by Asykur (2024). In his research entitled The Influence of Communication and Teamwork on Employee Performance at Lida Jaya Convection. This research is categorized as *field research*, with research instruments in the form of questionnaires, documentation, and observation, while the number of respondents was 60 employees of the Lida Jaya Garment Factory in Padurenan Gebog Kudus. The validity of the instruments was tested by comparing the r table (*degree of freedom*) with the r count (*Corrected Item Total Correlation*), while the reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha. The analysis technique used was the test of multiple linear regression at a significance level of 5%. The results of this study indicate that (1) the Communication Factor has a significant effect on Employee Performance with a t-value greater than the t-table ($3.327 > 1.672$), (2) the Teamwork Factor has a significant effect on Employee Performance with a t-value greater than the t-table ($1.945 > 1.672$), and (3) Communication and Teamwork Factors together have a significant effect on Employee Performance with a calculated f value greater than the table f value ($102.465 > 3.156$).

CONCLUSION

From the results of research on the Influence of Communication and Teamwork on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Secretariat and based on the results described in the previous chapter, the researcher can provide the following conclusions and suggestions: The study concludes that Communication and Teamwork are pivotal determinants of employee productivity. The Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of 0.560 demonstrates that these two variables explain 56% of the performance variance. Both partial and simultaneous statistical tests prove that improving interpersonal communication and fostering robust group cooperation will directly enhance the overall performance of the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat and Teamwork (Variable X2) simultaneously, and the remaining 44% is

determined by other factors not discussed in this study. The results of testing the research hypothesis prove that Communication (Variable X1) has an effect on Employee Performance (Variable Y). This result can be seen from the t-table value = 2.01410 and t-count = 4.348. Because t-count > t-table with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, the results of this hypothesis can state that Communication (Variable X1) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Variable Y). Thus, the first hypothesis (H1), which states that Communication Affects Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, is proven and accepted. The results of this research hypothesis testing prove that Teamwork (Variable X2) affects Employee Performance (Variable Y). This result can be seen from the t-table value = 2.01410 and t-count = 3.571. Because t-count > t-table with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$, the results of this hypothesis can state that Teamwork (Variable X2) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Variable Y). Thus, the results of the second hypothesis (H2), which states that there is an effect of teamwork on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, are proven and acceptable. The results of the hypothesis testing (F) in this study prove that Communication (Variable X1) and Teamwork (Variable X2) have an effect on Employee Performance (Variable Y) at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat (). Therefore, it can be said that with good communication and teamwork at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, employee performance will improve. This result can be seen from the F table value = 3.21 and F count = 29.634. Because F count > F table with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, the results of this hypothesis can state that Communication and Teamwork have a significant simultaneous effect on Employee Performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat. Thus, the results of the third hypothesis (H3), which states that there is an influence of communication and teamwork on employee performance at the Sibolga City Regional Secretariat, are proven and acceptable.

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